

The influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Teachers' Organizational Commitment: A Systematic Literature Review

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 15, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: January 17, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Transformational Leadership, teachers, school owners (principals), Organizational Commitment</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5860613</p>	<p><i>Leadership styles are the most crucial success factors of the organization. Kind of Leadership can be defined as the unique behaviours of leaders who lead, motivate, guide and manage people's groups. This study aimed to investigate the influence of transformational leadership style on teachers' organizational commitment. A systematic literature review methodology was adopted to investigate the impact of transformational leadership on teachers' organizational commitment. A rigorous article selection procedure was used from various journal databased to select ten research articles that fitted the inclusive criteria of this study. With the secondary schools and teachers' commitment on school organizational change, research was undertaken to evaluate the level of school principal transformational leadership. The outcomes of this study will inspire policy makers, educationists and school administrators to broaden transformational leadership by exploring theoretical processes explaining the connection and development of this process between transformational leadership styles used by school owners and teachers organizational commitment.</i></p>

Introduction

Due to its active involvement in the durability, effectiveness, and durability of any organization, work engagement has become one of the most significant fascinating problems that have piqued the interest of scholars. According to Luthans (2002), organizational commitment is the process through which members of an organization believe they have a stake in the organization's well-being and success and a sort of attitude that reflects that commitment. Leadership is one of the most important personal and organizational elements for organizational citizenship behaviour. In any educational establishment, Leadership is critical. It is an institution's route to prosperity or source of competitive advantage.

In an organizational environment, Leadership is a critical variable (Ocker et al., 2011). Leadership has a tremendous effect on the achievement and processes of team-based tasks (Horne, 2017). Leadership, along with directing, regulating, and organizing, was deemed a component of effective management in research by (Dimovski&colleagues, 2009). Several types of research (Manning and Robertson, 2011; Tucker and Lam, 2014) have emphasized the relevance of adaptive leadership styles and their adaptation. Different elements, such as tradition, circumstance, and demographics, influence this adaptation. Leadership styles play an essential role in all types and sizes of organizations. Moreover, we can say that Leaders may have a tremendous impact on the work environment, and their influence can increase or hamper the efficiency of people and task forces. Transactional, transformational, and ethical Leadership theories all require a consistent behaviour of the group leader more towards the teammates (Engelbrecht et al., 2017; Vito et al., 2014; Judge and Piccolo, 2004). Including these ideas, Leadership can only be described in terms of the leader's qualities or the characteristics of the circumstance. LMX (leader-member exchange) differs from the traditional dyadic interactions and incorporates them (Gerstner &Day, 1997).Leader-Member Exchange Theory (LMX) study has been conducted to understand the interactions between a leader and the employee. It is based on Social Exchange theories, which show that leaders treat people working in their field differently (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995). This unequal treatment causes substitute people, associated with the social exchanges with the supervisor, to become either in or out of the group. LMX is a spectrum that evaluates the significance of the interaction between the leading members from highest to lowest.

The leader's attitude is not identical with all members, as per Lunenburg, 2010); nevertheless, the leader establishes various connections and relations with each follower. This leadership approach is highlighted by the LMX theory (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995). According to LMX philosophy, each member develops a unique exchange connection with the leader. The nature of these ties varies from one follower to the next (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995). The leader develops in and out relational interactions with each follower during the relationship between the supervisor and subordinate. The leader delegated in-group members (high-quality

LMX) to influence the decision process. Participants from the out (low-quality LMX) are only responsible for their official written arrangement (Wayne, Shore, & Liden, 1997).

According to Northouse (2016) the LMX hypothesis works in two ways. It both dictates and characterizes Leadership. The leader develops in-group or out-group dyadic exchanges with each of the supporters, as per the LMX descriptive method. The qualitative approach of LMX is represented by the in-group and out-group development. The leader's trial to create memorable connections with each group member apart from the classification of in-group and out-group is referred to as the conventional theory to LMX. Customization is the focus of the prescriptive approach (Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1991a). The principal investigator, in this instance, prescribes their actions based on the connection. This doctorate dissertation is built on LMX's prescriptive methodology. This doctorate research is guided by LMX's prescribed method as an attempt to comprehend the desired phenomena. A team leader strives to create elevated relationships with all team members, according to the LMX framework's prescriptive approach (Northouse, 2016).

Leaders during exchanges of relationships can directly impact members' differing leadership styles regarding the sense of equality. Members who perceive substantial differentiation in management styles report poorer work satisfaction and well-being, suggesting that the LMX process and its results, directly and indirectly, affect accomplishments. If employees perceive, adverse effects may ensue. A supervisor in the whole Working Group differential styles. This also encourages the belief that LMX is not strictly anonymous but also involves open social events. Under a leader, it is evident to the whole working group. Past investigators have claimed that LMX represents a one-dimensional system comprising a fundamental indicator of leadership quality (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995; Liden & Maslyn, 1998; Scandura and Graen, 1984). The quality of LMX would be considered to consist of one aspect. While others have proposed LMX, a multidimensional review is used to help clarify how the participation, commitment and trust components are recognized (Dienesch & Liden, 1986). The virtues and drawbacks of each party were discussed, but none were accepted unanimously, and the unidirectional dispute led to a continuous evolution of LMX theory in the last 40 years (Schriesheim, Castro, & Cogliser, 1999).

Leadership is essential in every sector of any organization, including schools: 1) Instructional techniques 2) Academic achievement 3) School management 4) School climate. Because their leaders are accountable for the effectiveness and productivity of their subordinates, organizational success is dependent on their leadership styles (Saeed, Mahmood, & Ahmad, 2013). Teachers' organizational commitment is influenced by their leadership style (Saeed et al., 2013; Tabbodi, 2009). It is critical to the organizational progress since dedicated instructors are more effective as educators, which benefits pupils and programmes (Nordin, 2012).

Whereas if we talk about transformational Leadership, James MC Gregor Burns used transformational Leadership in a political setting for starters. On the other hand, Bernard Bass first used the term in an organizational environment (Makruf, 2017). Transformational Leadership is a type of Leadership that does not require the status quo to be maintained. It was primarily focused on attaining targets and taking measures following the organization's strategy to achieve previously unachieved goals. The term "transform" implies that modifications in organizational structure are required. In many scenarios, this Leadership does not hesitate to delegate high-level tasks/authority to subordinates (Andriani, Kesumawati & Kristiawan, 2018).

Transformational Leadership is being emphasized as one of the essential elements for improving an organization's overall performance. Due to its influence on teachers' behaviour and attitudes, recent studies have shown the relevance of Leadership in various organizations, including educational institutions. An analysis of the results reveals that organizational commitment and transformative Leadership have a favourable association (Acar, 2012; Avolio et al., 2004; Baek, 2012). Positive teacher work engagement enhances their quality and productivity by improving their attitudes toward their jobs (Baotham, 2011; Jing & Zhang, 2014).

The principals' leadership style changes depending on whether the school is making progress or not. The most excellent way to handle transformative Leadership is to restructure schools (Noraazian & Khalip, 2016). According to Yukl (2010) transformational leaders appealing to supporters' moral principles to increase their awareness, mobilize their capabilities and direct their energy toward transforming their organizations. This means that the transformational leader focuses on the individual employee rather than on the self to achieve the organization's many aims and outcomes. It's no surprise that transformational Leadership is among the most popular educational approaches.

Education in Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia's educational system is divided between the public and private sectors. The Ministry of Education (MOE) determines the curriculum that will be taught in public schools and the themes and concepts that will be covered. Furthermore, due to the rigorous monitoring of Ministry Supervisors on the public, MOE has a tight and robust form of control over public schools. In addition, the public sector's selection of leaders and teachers is opaque and differs depending on the nation's economic cities (Alkadi, 2020).

Faculties in Saudi Arabia are solely responsible for significant instructional responsibilities and are not involved in decision-making or other managerial problems (Allmnakrah & Evers, 2020). This may impact instructors' efficiency and achievement, which may have a detrimental impact on student's achievement. Teachers and top-

level executives of schools are the most significant element in improving the quality and education (Allmnakrah & Evers, 2020). The absence of cooperation among educational institutions remains the most critical obstacle to every new project (Alhammadi, 2017). This reflects the reality that educators cannot participate in progress even if they are dedicated and supported in their careers by the Education department, which views teachers as essential contributors to improving student achievement (Alyami, 2016).

The school administration did not communicate its objectives with instructors, even if they created goals that they thought appropriate for respective schools. As a result, according to the administration, school C had issues with teacher dedication and regulation. Many investigations have shown that the school leader influences teacher dedication and that excellent school leadership is essential for school success (Abu-Tineh, Khasawneh, & Al-Omari, 2008). Transformational leaders motivate their colleagues to complete projects and believe that their mission and ambition are essential in maintaining follower engagement.

According to Saudi Education's new vision, more emphasis should be placed on strengthening students' talents and growing their personalities. This also means the government recognizes the importance of character development and, more significantly, the teacher's involvement in students' achievement. Policymakers are concerned that the existing educational system fails to produce pupils with the abilities required for the country's economic success (Algraini & McIntyre-Mills, 2017).

Psychological Empowerment and Workplace Spirituality

Psychological empowerment is a subcategory of emancipation, which is a larger notion. Significance, capability, subconscious, and effect were the four cognitions they used to characterize psychological empowerment". (Kiv et al., 2019) A person's conviction in their capacity to do tasks successfully is referred to as proficiency. Because the individual's self-esteem is at stake, confidence refers to a sense of personal faith in the task's accomplishment. People with a high level of self-efficacy take action, make more significant contributions, and find success in the face of obstacles (Kiv et al., 2019). Another author emphasized the role and importance of competence in organizations, stating that individuals with a high level of self-efficacy take action, make more significant efforts, and succeed despite challenges and obstacles. Self-determination is a sense of control that arises from initiating and regulating behaviours(Thomas & Velthouse, 1990).

Workplace spirituality is described as a workspace that acknowledges that workers have an internal existence nurtured and fed by the worker, communities, and corporate meaning (Milliman, Czaplewski & Ferguson, 2003). Workplace spirituality is a new field of study that focuses on organizational outcomes like commitment. Employees consider helpful working conditions in line with their internal sentiments, and work and culture play a crucial part in achieving work-life balance (Amen & Raziq, 2019). The principal's promotion of the spiritual at school is necessary to establish and maintain a healthy workplace for workers. This is because workplace spirituality does indeed have a significant impact on school progress (Mydin et al., 2019).

Purpose of the Study

This systematic literature review aims to investigate the level of transformational leadership on teacher's organizational commitment in intermediate schools. The purpose of this systematic literature review study is to explore how transformational leadership influences organizational commitment. In addition, how transformational leadership conduct has a significant effect on subordinate views and how subsidiary properties and actions continue to affect their leadership perspectives. In this paper, we will conduct a systematic literature review by using transformational leadership style impact on teacher's organizational commitment.

This systematic review carefully examines the nature of the relationship between leaders and teachers' organizational commitment. We estimate ten studies on transformational leadership styles and their impact on teacher's organizational commitment employed randomized control tests (RCT) or quasi-experimental designs (QED) globally based on a preliminary Google Scholar search for about 3000 results. To respond to the research issues below, we propose that the systemic evaluation be extended and all relevant foreign studies are included.

Research Aim & Questions

The significant component of this qualitative approach, which is based on the leader-member exchange paradigm, is investigating the nature of relationships between leaders and teachers in intermediate schools'. Identifying the heart of the relationship might lead to some critical conceptual linkages that haven't been well investigated, such as conceptions that shape these interactions. Exploratory and explanatory research projects can be used to analyze such correlations further.

RQ: What is the impact of transformational Leadership on teachers' organizational commitment in intermediate school areas?

Our main goal for this research is to see what influence, if any, transformational Leadership has had on teacher's success in intermediate school areas. If obvious patterns emerge from a systematic review, we can try to offer strategies that mainly help teachers improve their performance.

Methodology/ Search Strategy

A literature review serves as a facilitator for creating theory, filling in any potential research gaps, and highlighting areas where even more or additional study is necessary inside the current literature on the subject

(Chen & Zheng, 2019). Systematic search techniques will be used to choose the studies. The foundations for searching are keywords and phrases selected to be as broad as possible for our first search. To prevent missing unpublished works owing to the file drawer problem, the search will cover both published and unpublished works. Literature evaluation, quality assessment, suitability and inclusion criteria, and the investigation included under qualitative research are the four key phases. The selectivity in a systematic review to discovery, screening, compilation, and a quick summary of diverse research is minimized by qualitative literature reviews. Therefore not only is a systematic review used to synthesize the most relevant findings from the literature, but it also allows for comparisons between researches (Nussbaum et al., 2019).

We used the terms ("leadership" or "transformational leadership") as keywords in Google Scholar for our exploratory search. We will conduct this systemic literature review on transformational Leadership because leadership styles are often referred to as transformational Leadership, Transactional Leadership, Ethical Leadership, and so on. As previously stated, we will conduct this systemic literature review on transformational Leadership, which is why we have changed our search parameters. The search phrases ("transformational leadership style's impact on teachers' organizational commitment") were used in JSTOR, ProQuest Databases, Ebsco Databases, and WorldCat databases. Alternatively, we also conducted a new search to get more relevant studies using the keyword (effect of transformational leadership style's on teachers' organizational commitment in intermediate school areas) to obtain all relevant results for my study subject.

Regarding the selection of final 10 papers (see table 1), the procedure is broken down into many phases. We had reduced the list down in stages after getting a list of all available relevant sources in Microsoft excel. In the excel sheet, we organized information of each studies including title, key words, instruments used in the published studies on transformational Leadership's influence based on teacher's organizational commitment, year of publication, research methods used, sample size and major findings. Titles were utilized in the first step to weed out irrelevant publications (for example, if the paper turns out to be related to transactional and ethical leadership styles instead of transformational). The content analysis was carried out in the second stage to identify and assess the critical research streams, reporting objectively on the various topics while highlighting potential research possibilities and difficulties (Rodrigues & Mendes, 2018). For this purpose, both researchers examined the abstracts to see if each paper may be eliminated. It was left until the following step if both researchers do not suggest removing it. Inside this third section, we will collect full-text papers and use the text to assess if the report should be included or not. To be eliminated, it needed to be determined by two researchers that it does not satisfy the search criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

Only experimental or quasi-experimental experiments focused or published from 2005 to onward were considered. The main emphasis was on the influence of transformative Leadership on teachers' organizational commitment in intermediate school areas, resulting in significant empirical discovery. The sample size of the treatment and control groups and attrition rates must be published in studies that establish baseline equivalence between the treatment and control groups. Only research that have been published in English were considered (or have available English translation). The study must have included demonstrated employee results, such as school teachers' behaviour toward their leaders and job efficiency.

Results

Our findings show that there are many pieces of research undertaken on the topic of transformational leadership impact on employee's performance in the organizations. It is an emerging trend in organizations to make their employees more committed and the best performer to achieve their goals efficiently and effectively. Modification is necessary for any company, and bringing the organization up to date and progressing with the age demands is an essential factor in any organization's success. As a robust development for mobilizing organizations, transformational Leadership is a crucial promoter of organizational change. Through inspiration and motivation, transformational leaders engage with their workers to bring about change. This is because transformational Leadership is defined as a leader who directs and motivates colleagues to work, communicates the school's purpose, and empowers them to realize its vision. The primary aim of this strategic literature review is to locate the whole work on transformational Leadership and its influence on workers throughout time. We have to go through 10 articles to conclude our findings. Ekpoh and Asuquo (2018) performed a study in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria; this study looked at secondary school principals' transformational leadership techniques and predicted organizational commitment and value reorientation among teachers. For the analysis, a survey design was used. A total of 799 instructors were chosen for the study using a stratified random selection approach from a population of 5,339 teachers. The study was driven by one research question and two hypotheses. The data was gathered using a 48-item questionnaire called the "Principals' Transformational Leadership Practices, Organizational Commitment, and Value Reorientation Questionnaire." The instrument's Cronbach Alpha dependability index was 0.88. The data were analyzed using various statistical techniques, including means, standard deviation, and regression analysis. The significance of the two hypotheses was evaluated at the 0.05 level. The results suggested that administrators' transformational leadership practises were high and that principals' practices substantially impacted organizational commitment and instructor value

readjustment. Based on the study results, secondary school administrators should support principals to embrace transformational leadership styles, which have been shown to influence commitment to the organization and teacher orientation reorientation.

Ling and Ibrahim (2013) performed a study. This paper aims to look at the link between secondary school teacher commitment and transformational leadership. A survey instrument was created based on a conceptual model for transformational leadership (Bass and Rigglo, 2006) and teacher commitment (Dannetta, 2002). With a pool of 1014 certified teachers teaching in twenty-seven secondary schools in Miri, Sarawak, a quantitative survey was used to investigate two generally predicted connections. The findings revealed that respondents had a moderate level of teacher dedication and a low level of transformational leadership skills. The analysis received minimal to medium support from the results of multiple regression analysis. They reveal how leadership strategies influence teachers' dedication. It also requires the creation of school administrators for them to develop transformational leadership characteristics, which are critical in altering teachers' attitudes and increasing their levels of commitment.

Another study by Konsolas, Anastasiou, Loukeri(2014) was conducted on the impact of Leadership on the effectiveness of teachers. The most common conclusion to be drawn from the above is that practises like educator motivation, job satisfaction in the workplace, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship, and teacher leadership are just a few of the leading factors that are thought to have a strong impact on teacher autonomy. What's more, according to the literature and data, transformational Leadership appears to encompass all of the relevant behaviours that significantly impact teachers' performance. However, regardless of the leadership paradigm used, this might be beneficial if the proper processes were followed. Additionally, a study conducted by (Abdullah et al., 2017)consists on the Impact of Transformational Principal Leadership on Teacher Commitment and School Performance, with Secondary School and Teachers Commitment on School Organizational, a research was undertaken to evaluate the extent of school principal transformational leadership. This study employs the survey technique, which entails the distribution of questionnaires. This study's questionnaire is broken into three sections. The demographics of the respondents are covered in the first section of the questionnaire. The second part of the research topic consists of 20 different aspects of teacher commitment (1990). The third section of the study question comprises 20 elements that characterize the transformational leadership style depending on Bass and Avolio's instruments (1995). A total of 217 people contributed to the study's success, with two forms of statistics being used: descriptive analysis and parameter estimation. According to the findings, the majority of respondents choose to stimulate the intellectual dimension (6:09 min) above the trigger motivation dimension (5.98 min), individual consideration dimensions (5.88 min), and charismatic dimension (5.88 min) (mean 5.40). The fourth pillar of transformative Leadership is to stimulate the mind. There was no substantial difference in organizational citizenship behaviour and gender ($t(97) = 1.561$, $p > 0.05$) when T-tests were done. However, the reliability test revealed that transformational Leadership has a significant association with ($r = 0.431$). Principals' roles and responsibilities must also be modified from time to time, and they must attempt to modify under time and situation. The purpose and vision of creating an exceptional school will be realized if the principal possesses successful leadership traits. On the other hand, if a principal exhibits the qualities of poor Leadership, it will harm a school's success. Further study Mohammed, Othman and Mahazan (2018) performed research on The Impact of Transformational Leadership Dimensions on Teacher Performance in Yemeni Public Schools;the purpose of this study was to look at the impact of various aspects of transformational Leadership on teacher performance in Yemeni public schools. The questionnaires were sent to Yemeni public schools in Sana'a, Republic of Yemen, to represent the sample. Three hundred seventy-four participants were chosen as part of the sample, which included both employees and instructors. The methodology used was a 5-point Likert scale from a questionnaire, which was analyzed with smartpls3. All elements of transformational Leadership have a beneficial impact on teachers' achievement, according to the findings. Moreover Noraaziani and Khalip(2016) performed a research study on In Malaysian Public Schools, the Impact of Transformational Leadership and Teacher Commitment demonstrates the teachers' views in the selected public schools. The. The study explored the influence of transformational Leadership its dimensions on dedication. The study population was all of the teachers at New Deal's Perak School. The Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) and the three-component model of work engagement survey were used to examine the link between transformational support and management in 317 primary school teachers. To examine the data, the correlation coefficient was employed. According to the findings, the headmasters' high degree of transformational Leadership substantially impacted teachers' commitment. The study's second finding suggested that transformational Leadership had a substantial impact on teachers' dedication. Innovative thinking, idealized influenced conduct, inspirational drive, and individualized concern were all linked with instructors' dedication. In this regard, the third finding suggested that the transformational leadership component of contingent compensation benefited the instructors' engagement to some level.Kenneth and Doris (2000) performed research on Transformational Leadership's influence on organizational circumstances and student engagement with the school. Their research findings demonstrate that most school restructuring initiatives assume significant capacity development on the part of individuals and entire organizations; they also rely on

high levels of motivation and commitment to solving the significant problems associated with restructuring initiatives' implementation. Under these circumstances, transformational leadership techniques have long been recommended as effective, and the study indicates that transformational practices help the growth of capability and engagement. However, there is far less data on whether these socio-psychological impacts lead to organizational change and quality care. The relative impacts of transformative leadership techniques on selected organizational circumstances and student engagement with school were investigated using survey data from an achieved sample of 1,762 teachers and 9,941 students in one large school system. The findings revealed that such Leadership has substantial effects on organizational conditions and modest but still substantial total impact on student commitment. Ahmad et al., (2019) accomplish research on The Impact of Transformational Leadership Skills on Secondary School Teachers' Performance in Punjab. The study investigates the impact of a principal's transformational leadership abilities on teaching effectiveness at the secondary level in Punjab. The impact of a superintendent's transformational leadership qualities, such as idealized influence and inspiring motivation, on teacher performance, was investigated. The study also aims to determine the number of transformational leadership abilities possessed by principals, as well as how these two talents, when employed separately and together, influence the effectiveness of secondary school teachers. To perform this study, a sample of 223 administrators of public secondary schools was chosen. The principal's two transformative leadership qualities and the instructors' performance were measured using two self-developed questionnaires as a research instrument. The data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, linear, and multiple regressions. The current study's findings revealed that both transformational leadership qualities sub and affect teacher performance. Impossibly perfect impact and inspiring commitment were shown to be the most important determinants of teacher effectiveness.

One more study stated by Alan (2005) entails the impact of several forms of intermediate principal leadership activities on components of a school's educational setting, and chosen teacher achievements are investigated in this study. A quantitative examination of teachers' views of administrators' leadership style, classroom learning atmosphere, and chosen teacher objectives was conducted in Study 1 using an instrument administered in 52 randomly selected schools and including 458 teachers from New South Wales, Australia. Study 2 examined those leadership behaviours that increased or degraded teachers' impressions of the school learning environment and teacher satisfaction, based on data obtained from 12 respondents in three schools. The qualitative part of the research was utilized to look at those particular key leadership positions. Practices that improve teacher results as well as student views of classroom instruction surroundings. These findings are relevant for individuals in positions of power in schools, and they contradict the conclusions of transformational leadership research. Practitioners will appreciate modifying leadership behaviours xviii to meet particular school educational environments and teacher output goals. In contrast, those participating in leadership training will understand the power of the transformational and transactional paradigms' behavioural elements.

Finally, the previous research conducted by (Zamira and Linda, 2021) on the Impact of School Principal Leadership's Transformational and Transactional Attributes on Teachers' Work Motivation the purpose of this study is to determine the influence of school principal leadership's transformational and transactional characteristics on teachers' intention of working. The Work Tasks Motivation Scale for Teachers (WTMST) and the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire examined 357 Kosovar public middle school teachers (MLQ). According to the findings, individual consideration predicts motivation for supplementary tasks and performance appraisal representations of the real reason for student evaluations. Transformational leadership attributes, idealized influence, and inspirational inspiration all indicate autonomous motivation in teachers.

Table 1
List of Final Studies Extracted for Systematic Literature Review

No	Author	Year published	Study Variables	Methodology Used	Findings
1	UduakEkpoh, Michael Asuquo	2018	Principals' Transformational Leadership Practices As Determinants Of Organizational Commitment And Value Reorientation	Nigeria. Survey design was adopted for the study. Seven hundred and ninety-nine respondents were drawn using stratified random sampling technique from a population of 5,339 teachers. An instrument with 48 items titled "Principals' Transformational Leadership Practices, Organizational Commitment and Value Reorientation Questionnaire" was utilized for data gathering.	Principals' transformational leadership practices were high, while there was a significant effect of principals' transformational leadership practices on organizational commitment and value reorientation of teachers.
2	<u>Sii Ling and Mohammed Ibrahim</u>	2013	Transformational Leadership and Teacher Commitment	A survey instrument was developed, based on conceptual framework on transformational leadership (Bass and Rigglo, 2006), and teacher commitment (Dannetta, 2002). Quantitative survey method was applied and two broadly hypothesized relationships were tested with a sample of 1014 trained teachers serving in twenty-seven secondary schools in Miri, Sarawak.	A moderate level of teacher commitment and a low level of transformational leadership qualities among the respondents. The results from multiple regression analysis provided little to moderate support for the analysis.
3	KonsolasEmmanouil, AnastasiouOsia MA, LoukeriParaskevi-Ioanna	2014	Impact of Leadership on Teachers'	The continuous and intensive socio-economic changes have created the need of restructuring educational practices as well as the structures of the schools. New challenges have been introduced aiming not only to improve the educational outcomes but also to achieve the adaptation to the new community needs. In the educational arena, teacher is the mediator, the person that expresses the evolutions and transforms them to knowledge.	The involvement of educational leader in the teacher's educational process. Leadership policy is a crucial factor for the teacher's effectiveness. Some practices, in relation with Leadership policy, are proved that contribute to teacher's empowerment.
4	Abdullah Ibrahim, Wan Khairul Aiman Wan Mokhtar, Suzaike Ali, Mohamad HafisAmatSimin	2017	Transformational Principal Leadership Style, Teachers Commitment	The questionnaire used in this study is divided into three parts. The first part of the questionnaire are questions about the demographics of the respondents. Part two of the study question, is 20 items teacher commitment dimensions (1990). While the third part of the research question contains 20 items that describe the transformational leadership style based on instruments built by Bass and Avolio (1995). A total of 217 respondents had cooperated in the success of this study.	The correlation test showed a significant relationship between transformational leadership with ($r = 0.43$). In relation to the roles and responsibilities of principals also need to be changed from time to time and they have to try to change according to time and circumstances. If a principal has the characteristics of effective leadership, the mission and the vision to make an excellent school will be achieved.
5	Mohammed Alzoraiki, Mahazan A. Mutalib, Othman bin Ab. Rahman	2018	Transformational Leadership, Teachers' Performance	A total of 374 respondents were selected which include staff and teachers as the sample. The instrument used was a Likert 5-point scale from the questionnaire which were examined using smartpls.	All the dimensions of transformational leadership have a positive influence on the teachers' performance.
6	Noraazian, Khalip	2016	Transformational Leadership, Teacher Commitment	The targeted population consisted of all teachers in New Deal's school in Perak. The sample was made up of 317 teachers from secondary schools to study the relationship	The headmasters' high degree of transformational Leadership substantially impacted teachers' commitment. Moreover,

				between transformational leadership and commitment using the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ).	transformational leadership had a substantial impact on teachers' dedication. Likewise, the transformational leadership component of contingent compensation benefited the instructors' engagement to some level.
7	Kenneth_Leith wood_,Doris_Ja ntzi	2000	transformational leadership ,organizational conditions and student engagement	Survey data from an achieved sample of 1,762 teachers and 9,941 students in one large school district were used to explore the relative effects of transformational leadership practices on selected organizational conditions and student engagement with school.	Results demonstrated strong significant effects of such leadership on organizational conditions, and moderate but still significant total effects on student engagement.
8	Ahmad, Muhammad Shafiq; Bakhsh, Khuda; Rasool, Shafqat	2019	Transformational Leadership Skills, Teachers' Performance	A sample of 223 principals of public secondary schools was taken to complete this study. Two self-developed questionnaires were used as a research instrument to measure the two transformational leadership skills of the principal and the teachers' performance. Mean, standard deviation, linear and multiple regressions were used for data analysis.	Two transformational leadership skills have a significant effect on the teacher performance. It was concluded that idealized influence and inspirational motivation are the dominant predictors of the teacher performance.
9	Alan M. Barnett	2005	Transformational Leadership Style of the School Principal, School Learning Environments and Selected Teacher Outcomes	A quantitative examination of teachers' views of administrators' leadership style in two studies: Study 1, using an instrument administered in 52 randomly selected schools and including 458 teachers from New South Wales, Australia. Study 2 examined those leadership behaviours that increased or degraded teachers' impressions of the school learning environment and teacher satisfaction.	Those participating in leadership training will understand the power of the transformational and transactional paradigms' behavioural elements.
10	ZamiraHyseni Duraku and Lin da Hoxha	2021	Transformational and Transactional Attributes of School Principal Leadership, Teachers' Motivation for Work	A sample of 357 Kosovar public middle school teachers was assessed using the Work Tasks Motivation Scale for Teachers (WTMST) and the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ).	Transformational leadership attributes, idealized influence, and inspirational motivation predict autonomous motivation in teachers; individual consideration predicts motivation for complementary tasks; and contingent reward significantly predicts motivation for student evaluations.

Conclusion

This systematic literature review has been performed by using ten research articles from 2005 to onward; research findings of all research papers demonstrate that transformational Leadership of school principals and owners plays an essential and positive role in teachers' motivation towards their work goals. More adaptable, open-minded, responsive to individual requirements, promoting active involvement and cooperation, partnering in judgments, and having a high tolerance for risk are all characteristics of transformational Leadership (Surbhi, 2015). All of these characteristics help teachers to increase their involvement in participation in decision making regarding student achievements. According to the conclusions of a study, transformational Leadership is the most effective approach to create changes in the educational environment. Leadership has the knowledge and abilities to adjust to new environments constantly (Cherry, 2006). In short, we can say that transformational Leadership plays an essential role in teachers' organizational commitment in schools.

This SLR focuses on teachers' actions in school and their understanding of transformational leadership qualities. It does, however, have significant flaws that should be taken into account in future research. Because just ten

research articles were employed in this study, it is advised that a more substantial number of publications be used to achieve more detailed results in future work.

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